

POLYTHELIA IN A THIRTEEN-YEAR-OLD GIRL AS A CAUSE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL MANIFESTATION AT MBALE TERTIARY HOSPITAL, UGANDA: A CASE REPORT

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Abstract- Polythelia is defined as presence of a third or more nipples in a human being, this term polythelia is derived from the Greek language, meaning many nipples.

At times this term is used interchangeably with the term polymastia which means presence of more than two breasts in an individual, however these two conditions can occur concurrently.

We report a case of a 13-year-old girl who presented with history of having been born with extra nipples, which were noticed at birth by the mother the mother was not bothered because the girl was growing normally compared to other girls who were born in the same period.

Nevertheless, the mother began getting worried about the girl's condition when the girl, started complaining to her that her breasts were different from those of other girls, she further reported that her peers and pupils in upper primary classes were telling that her condition was associated with things like curses, and fertility.

Subsequently these complaints were followed by self-isolation from the peers, putting on overfitting clothes and reduced participation in classroom activities and this tremendously affected her performance in academics.

The polythelia was treated by simple bilateral excisions without intra or post operative complications, the tissue was subjected to histology and tissue showed ducts within stroma with normal epidermis overlying the stroma which confirmed a diagnosis of polythelia.

In subsequent follow-up, abdominal ultrasound showed no associated abdominal abnormalities and had improved happily associating with peers and active in class activities.

Introduction

Polythelia which as described by various terms such as third nipple, extra nipple, exanumerary nipples nipple, was derived from the Greek language and literature shows that it was described in the books of medicine way back in 1150 (1)

The epidemiology documented in literature varies tremendously. For instance, studies in Hungarian children gives a prevalence of 4.3%. Pietro and coworkers documented an occurrence of polythelia 0.2to 5.5% in the general population (2)

In Africa, East Africa and Uganda , there is no documented and published studies concerning polythelia. This appears the first case to be documented in Uganda.

In this case of 13 year presented to us with clear symptoms of psychological problems which started manifesting a year before and these symptoms were relieved with a simple bilateral excision

Case Report

Partial Information

13years old female, a primary five pupil, with extra nipple noticed by the mother at birth, presented in surgical outpatient following change in dressing code and withdraw from associating with the peers and feeling shy to participate in class hence declining in her school performance to which the mother initially attributed to a child being stubborn and insubordinate

Clinical Findings

They included,

The girl was shy, dressed in over fitting jacket, rarely looked at the examining doctor's face.

Two Extra nipples were seen with each lying below the normal nipple and were having well developed areola.

Measurements

The right was 2 X 3 X 6cm and the left was 2 X 3 X5 cm.

Other systems were normal

Timeline

On 10 September 2023, patient was admitted. Workup done on 12 September 2023, excision of both extra nipples was done without any intra operative or post operative complications. The patient was discharged on oral antibiotics and analgesics on 14th of September 2023.

The first follow-up, the wounds were dry and clean, 21st of September. The second follow-up the patient was well dressed and able to look at the examining doctor, 5th December.

Diagnostic Assessment

Blood tests revealed a total white blood cell count $8.2 \times 10^9 / l$ with a normal absolute leucocyte values and hemoglobin of 12.0 g/dl, Urea was 7.50mmol/L and creatinin of 124.5 umol/l. Urine Analysis showed microscopic hematuria (25 RBCs/HPF) and plus cells (20 WBCs /HPF). The abdominal ultra sound showed normal kidneys, ureters, urinary bladder and uterus.

Pathology Results showed ducts within stroma with normal epidermis overlying the stroma which confirmed a diagnosis of polythelia

Therapeutic Intervention

Antibiotics given Oral capsules Ampiclox 500mg 6 hourly for 7 days, Tabs Ibuprofen 400mg 8 hourly for 5 days.

Follow up and Outcome

Post-operative hospital care was uneventful. The patient was discharged with oral antibiotics on the second day.

Figure 1. Histology result showing diagnosis of polythelia

Her school progress before operation.**PROGRESSIVE REPORTS**

P3/4

SUBJECT	FIRST TERM %	SECOND TERM %	THIRD TERM %
Mathematics	48	46	37
English	40	31	33
Science	20	26	21
Social studies	52	24	38
RE	37	30	

Figure 2. Showing Patients Primary Three progressive Performance

Her school progress after the operation.

P5

SUBJECT	FIRST TERM %	SECOND TERM %	THIRD TERM %
Subject	First term	Second term	Third term
Mathematics	31	23	45
English	44	47	36
Science	18	28	31
Social studies	25	32	39

Figure 3 Showing Patients Primary Five Progressive Results

Discussion

Polythelia is defined as presence of a third or more nipples in a human being, this term polythelia is derived from the Greek language, meaning many nipples. It is documented as being more common in males than female (3). This in

agreement with other studies done by other scholars. (4) (5) It has been observed as surgical condition which would warrant surgical intervention for cosmetic purposes

However, the patient had psychological clinical presentation which were relieved by simple surgical intervention. The declining academic performance also improved as show in figure 3

This appears to be the first case to be documented in Mbale regional referral hospital and therefore over case is adding knowledge to the existing and makes this a case for publication

Conclusion

Polythelia is relatively uncommon with non-specific clinic presentation except for pain at puberty and during pregnancy, however these patients can present with psychological manifestation like in our case study. This psychological manifestation can b managed by simple surgical excision of the polythelia which can relieve psychological symptoms.

Patient Perspective

The patient was very happy with outcome of surgical intervention.

Consent

A written informed consent was received from the parent of the patient and can be presented incase wanted by the editor.

Authors Contribution

Francis Owori Riwo, Abingwa John Patrick, Elwana Moses Okware Patrick and Mbale Regional Referral Hospital Nurses. All authors contributed in literature review, manuscript writing and review.

Competing Interest

The authors have no financial, consultative, institutional and other relationships that might lead bias or conflict of interest.

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